

POTATO DISEASE CLASSIFICATION USING DEEP LEARNING: A CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK APPROACH

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Abstract

The quantity and quality of potato yields are significantly impacted by two types of disease, the early blight, and the late blight, and these diseases are difficult to interpret, time-consuming, and inconvenient. Fortunately, the easy way to detect the disease is through leaf appearance using appropriate models in potato plants. Production of potatoes will substantially rise if the infections are detected early to infect any potato plants. With the help of different models of computer vision and deep learning techniques were used earlier to classify potato diseases from potato leaf images, to produce healthy foods, and to decrease the loss of yields. CNN is the most effective for the classification of potato leaf disease with high accuracy and low loss rate, the faster-converging rate achieved by the deep learning models.

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INTRODUCTION

Potato is formerly the most significant food-crop worldwide after wheat and rice and half of its production currently occurs in developed countries. Potato is a versatile agricultural commodity and plays a vital role in contributing to national income, the diseases in potatoes are mainly common in potato crops cause of Bacterial and fungal processes. Leaves disease are among the most mutually critical disease [1].

Here, we discuss only two types of potato diseases in this paper which are the vulnerable diseases in potato crop yield. Potato early blight disease, and late blight disease are one of the important issues in potato crop diseases and these diseases are essential for effective on our country economy,

and also harmful for farmers. The oldest method for recognizing these diseases is dependent on a physical inspection by a former or any expert to reach the crop areas. However, deep learning gives us a mechanized process to develop an application to identify late blight and early blight diseases easily.

AI technology has developed the way we work, learn, and extract knowledge. After the conclusion of numerous technologies, we reached that point where that field increased crucially over two decades. Data science and AI had a profound impact on issues in social, cultural, and scientific fields, as well as the area of agriculture. Data science and AI present

challenges and opportunities to improve the operation which is very difficult to do by human minds.

Deep learning has emerged as a well-known technique in image classification, and its application has extended to the field of agriculture, to examine the usage of deep learning in agriculture faces various challenges, among which early blight and late blight are particularly significant potato disease that require timely detection, that practice will be beneficial to promoting the development of a sustainable agricultural field, these small steps ensure food safety and save human health, and it hold social and economic values. This research paper, suggest the CNN technique for classifying the affected plants of potato diseases. In particular, we examine the different applications and models of transfer learning and CNN for the systematic categorizing of early and late blight diseases found in potato leaves. The main aim is to provide efficient and useful method that enables farmers to responds rapid action on potato diseases. We found some transfer learning model, methods, and CNN has the potential to improving efficacy, and accuracy of diseases in potatoes and reduce the loss of crop yields. With the capacity to remove the complex patterns and outlines of features from limited datasets, the popular model we found nowadays is the deep learning model often working with graphical tasks we need a convolution neural network. CNN can classify the features of photos and make them perfect for the classification of potato leaf diseases. All of these issues are fairly handled by the convolutional neural network, which also has a higher accuracy rate than a typical classifier. We employed VGG16 to find the disease on potato leaves for the incredible performance of the disease classification technique of CNN.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

In previous years, many investigators have utilized machine learning to identify potato leaf diseases and fix problems in order to improve crops for potato output. Deep learning allows them to use many methods to extract the features

of each disease in a short time and with accurate results, and with this strategy, they have succeeded in creating many applications and webs that help farmers and peasants detect the situation of plants early. In this chapter, we discuss the related work and articles, this literature review helps to understand the issues occur during the processing and identification of potato leaf diseases and an overview of the problems that involved due to the increase in the number of interests in deep learning models and computer vision algorithms, efficiency and effectiveness. In the outcome, the knowledge shared by different authors and scholars be discussed below.

Used an ANN classifier for the early prediction of potato leaf diseases from datasets. FFNN Model is used for this purpose and accuracy is 96% [2]. Used a CNN model for potato leaves diseases classification and achieved 94% accuracy. [3]. Used the pre-trained Dense net for potato leaves disease detection with an accuracy of 97%. [4]. Created a CNN model to classify potato leaves diseases compared accuracy with the pre-trained models VGG-16, Resnet, and Google net on the same dataset and achieved 97% accuracy [5]. Used CNN model for the detection of potato leaves diseases with an accuracy of 91% [6]. Used SVM for the classification of potato leaf disease detection and the accuracy is 95% [7]. Use image preprocessing and machine learning methods to detect potato leaf diseases where RF obtained a higher accuracy of 97% [8]. Using a customized convolutional neural model with 04 convolutional layers, and 04 max pool layers for the identification of diseases from potato leaves. The accuracy is obtained up to 97% for training data and 92% for validation, data batches equal to 20 at 10 epochs [9]. Build a customized CNN model named sequential model and data augmentation technique for potato leaves disease classification. The customized model achieves a good result with an accuracy of 97% compared to per-trained models [10]. Use the deep learning CNN model VGG-16 and VGG-19 to classify the potato leaves disease and the average accuracy is 91% [11]. Using the machine learning method for this

process and the SVM and achieved a good result with the highest accuracy 97% [12]. We used a deep learning-based method to identify the potato leaf disease and an overall accuracy of 97% [13][14]. Used ShuffleNetV2 to detect potato late blight disease. Used the machine learning method to identify potato diseases from potato disease images [15]. Identify different types of potato leaves disease by using a deep learning based multi-level model [16]. Used two deep CNN models MobileNetV2, and Nasnet Mobile with the data augmentation technique for potato leaf disease detection [17]. Used the transfer learning with a pre-trained model for flower classification and got the high performance achieved with the VGG-16 model at a rate of 93% [18]. Used a deep learning CNN model named Alex-Net for the detection of apple leaf disease with an overall accuracy of 97% [19]. Used a machine learning method named deep forest for the identification of disease from maize leaf and compared it with other methods and the highest accuracy is 96% achieved from the deep forest [20].

By using different types of robots with using different machine learning approaches the diseases will detect in a good manner [21]. Used transfer learning for the automated disease classification of crops in the field of agriculture. Diseases are classified using some pre-trained models with data augmentation techniques [22]. Used the CNN model with transfer learning

techniques for the identification of many types of plant diseases from leaf images and the EfficientNetBo model has acquired the highest accuracy with 99% through four different models [23].

A transfer learning approach was applied for identification of diseases from rice plants. In this method AlexNet was used for finding the features while SVM support vector machine was employed for disease identification, and the model accuracy achieved by 91%, by allocating 80% of dataset for training, and remaining 20% of dataset for testing [24]. Additionally, a deep learning-based model was implemented for recognizing of crop leaf disease [25]. The android app for like [26] is need to introduce for helping farmers.

The work related to potato leaf disease detection is summarized in Table 1.

At this stage, we find the best performance of different CNN models in this experiment by both qualitative and quotative approaches as well as visually. We observed that the CNN model and transfer learning model called Dense net, and VGG-16 were used in this project. The transfer learning model reached the highest accuracy of 97% on the plant village dataset table number 5 shows the different work done by other scholars for potato leaf disease classification from images.

References	DataSource	Model	Accuracy
KUMAR SANJEEV [2]	Plant Village	FFNN, Features extraction (Color, texture, shape)	96%
Dr. Tejashree T. Moharekar [3]	Plant Village	CNN, Deployment by Streamlit	94%
RabbiaMahumaet [4]	Plant Village, and captured by camera	Dense net	97%
Deep Kothari [5]	Plant Village	CNN Model	97%
AnushkaBangal [6]	Plant Village	CNN Model named Sequential Model	91%
A. Singh, H. Kaur [7]	Plants Village	Classification by SVM, feature extraction (Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix)	95%
Md. A. Iqbal, K. H. Talukder [8]	Plant Village, and Database (450 images)	KNN, Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, (RF) Random Forest, SVM	RF-97%
Md. K. R. Asif [10]	Kaggle, Dataquest, and some manual images	Customized CNN named Sequential Model, Data Augmentation	97%
R. A. Sholihati1 [11]	Potato plantation in Malang, Indonesia, and Google images	VGG16, VGG19	91%

Table no. 1 Summary on comparative analysis work in potato leaf disease classification.

II.PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Methodology Flowchart
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This research paper proposed the CNN architecture with 07 convolutional layers and 03 dense layers. The softmax classifier is applied in the last layer to categorize the effected region. Each convolutional layer incorporates ReLU, a nonlinear activation function that helps to prevent the vanishing gradient issue by converting negative inputs to the zero. To reduce computational load and the spatial dimensions of the data, a pooling layer is placed after each convolution. Max pooling is employed to down sampling the feature maps, which helps to minimizing overfitting and boosts the efficiency of the activation function, leading to faster model convergence. Ultimately in final stage, a fully connected (dense) layer is used to classify the potato leaf images, utilizing a softmax function to produce one of three possible class predictions.

- i. Input Layer:** the accepted picture size by our model is 256 x 256.
- ii. Convolutions and Pooling Layer:** input images are directly used for feature extraction by neurons with relu operation using CNN.
- iii. Platten Layer:** Flatten layers transform the output derived from convolutional layers into one dimensional vector.
- iv. Fully connected Layers:** After each convolution layers and max pool are incorporated with diminished spatial dimensions.
- v. Output Layers:** The concluding the result by last layer is comprised of three neurons, aligning with three distinct disease classes e.g., potato

healthy, early blight, and late blight, and employs softmax activation for classification.

vi. **Model Compilation:** during the compilation, the model will employ the Adam optimizer in conjunction with categorical cross-entropy loss suitable

Figure 2: system model for classification of potato diseases images

In this research paper, we employ convolutional neural network (CNNs) for the recognition of disease from potato leaf and classify them. The model leverages the strength of deep and high dimensional aspects play a leading role for the detection and categorization of disease, which is crucial for precise identification and classification of plants diseases found from potato plant. Deep learning model are famous and well-known for their ability as feature extraction from pictures and classify them into

three different classes. In this research paper, a technique for the identification of potato disease is employed using modified CNN model architecture. The overall process for this research comprises of following four phases such as 1) Data Gathering, 2) Preprocessing, 3) Training, and 4) Classification. After data collection and pre-processing steps performed like normalization to improve the image visibility and resizing to standard dimensions were prepare the image for training and classification.

Figure 3: different photos of Potato Leaf disease

Choice for tasks involving multiclass classification. Throughout the training, the accuracy metric is employed to oversee the model performance. With the architecture we used in the CNN model, we found more than one lakh

83 thousand parameters, using Adam optimizer functions, the learning rate value, and the same epoch's size is equal to 30. The results of our program are described in Table 3.

Optimizer Function	Batch Size	Epochs	Validation Loss	Validation Accuracy
Adam	32	5	0.5480	0.7865
Adam	32	30	0.0178	0.9848

Table 2 Training and Testing Accuracy on Different Epoch Number

III. RESULTS WITH TRANSFER LEARNING

In summary, based on the data, dense net consistently performs well across different batch

sizes, demonstrating high accuracy and low loss value. On the other hand, VGG-16 shows relatively stable performance with similar loss and accuracy values.

#	References	DataSource	Model	Accuracy
1	KUMAR SANJEEV [2]	Plant Village	FFNN, Features extraction	96%
2	Dr. Tejashree T. Moharekar [3]	Plant Village	CNN	94%
3	RabbiaMahumaet [4]	Plant Village	DenseNet-201	97%
4	AnushkaBangal [6]	Plant Village	CNN	91%
5	Md. Khalid Rayhan Asif [5]	Kaggle	Customized CNN	97%
6	R. A. Sholihati1 [11]	Google mages	VGG16	91%
7	Proposed Model	Plant Village	CNN	98%

Table 3 Compression with other Transfer Learning Models

Table no. 4 Comparison among Different Models

IV. CONCLUSION

To find out Potato leaves disease illness without any systematic system is too difficult and error-prone process. But if we do the same work with technology to give reliable results and save our work time and resources, also this process will lead to a significant

boost in the production of potato crops yield and gross improvement in the country's economy. In the project transfer learning methods can be applied in the agricultural domain can save the waste of fruits and vegetables. Transfer learning is a pre-trained model that performs the extreme on unseen leaf

disease datasets. In the future, the proposed method can be integrated into a web application or and mobile application will make a revolution in the agriculture domain.

In the proposed work, we carried out through analysis of two transfer learning models for the classification of potato diseases, namely dense net, and VGG-16. The performance of each model was assessed and the findings produced some insightful information. Dense net outperformed the other evaluated models, achieving a remarkable accuracy. This shows that Dense Net is very good at correctly classifying various diseases in potato leaf diseases. Following the VGG-16 model accuracy was good further demonstrating its prowess in disease classification. Along with the transfer learning models a straightforward CNN model was also used, and it managed to achieve a perfect accuracy of 98 percent this can be attributed to the relatively smaller input size used for training and testing. It is clear from the results of the testing and training phase that VGG-16 consistently provided excellent performance across the evaluated models. As a result, we can state with confidence that VGG-16 is the best option for this dataset because it provides a high level of classification accuracy and reliability. Deep learning techniques have the potential to help farmers and researchers identify diseases early, facilitate prompt interventions, and reduce the impact of diseases on potato yield, as demonstrated by the successful supplication of transfer learning models, particularly dense net and VGG-16. The implementation of intelligent decision support systems for efficient disease management in potatoes may result from further study and development in this field.

V. FUTURE WORKS

Deep learning is a good technological technique for the detection of disease and its easy-to-use transfer learning models are so helpful because they can give good results in different cases depending on whether the size of the new images or the background is complex or simple and the size of the dataset. Some studies used simple background and simple deep learning models, such as KNN, SVM, and XGB, and they achieved good results [38]. However, transfer learning models like VGG-16, and dense net also

give us better outcomes [39]. And many studies used the same dataset with the same transfer learning models but obtained different results. Like our study, as a result, we should always try new models with the same dataset because this allows us to find the better model and decrease the error value.

In this paper, the results show us many important points on which we should focus. The aim is to identify the different diseases in potato leaves and to achieve this, we used some deep learning models (VGG-16, and Dense net) in many papers to find the highest accuracy value and lowest value for loss. But we didn't find the same results. Just with VGG-16, we found a better outcome with accuracy equal to 97 percent and loss equal to 0.097 percent.

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